

DYNAMIC DEFORMATION MONITORING OF GFRP BEAM USING OPTICAL FIBER DISTRIBUTED SENSING SYSTEM BASED ON OPTICAL FREQUENCY DOMAIN REFLECTOMETRY

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ABSTRACT

This paper demonstrates the dynamic identification of the deformation of glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) in the state of vibration using an optical fiber distributed sensing system. We develop the optical fiber distributed sensing system which is capable of measuring the dynamic strain distribution based on optical frequency domain reflectometry. We embed a fiber Bragg grating (FBG) with a continuous sensing range of more than 40 cm into glass fiber fabric and co-cure with epoxy. A GFRP laminate integrated with the FBG is cut into a beam. We apply vibrations of the resonant frequencies to the beam, and measure the strain distribution with a measurement rate of more than 800S/s. We calculate the deformation of the GFRP beam based on the measured strain distribution. We compare the results with the observed deformation by a high-speed camera and a laser displacement sensor. The applicability of the sensing system for the dynamic deformation monitoring of composites is investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Dynamic deformation of composite structural parts such as wind turbine blades and aircraft wings is the essential parameter to be monitored for the purpose of structural health monitoring and feedback for future structural design and appropriate operation. Optical fiber sensors (OFSs) have been expected as a promising sensing method for this purpose of deformation estimation. Optical fibers can be embedded into the composite, which does not harm the fluid flow around the structural parts [1]. In addition, some OFSs can measure the distributed profiles of strains, based on which the deformation can be calculated with high accuracy. Representative techniques for the distributed sensing are optical frequency domain reflectometry (OFDR) [2-4]. Sensing techniques based on OFDR achieve high spatial resolutions up to sub-mm order which enable us to detect initial damage of structural parts and to estimate structural response such as deformation with high accuracy [5].

When it comes to the application of the distributed sensing system of OFSs, however, there have been only a few examples for dynamic deformation monitoring [6-8]. This is mainly because of the limited sweep speed of the conventional laser source and the calculation cost for the signal processing to demodulate distributed data. Some studies are currently conducted to overcome such bottlenecks [9].

In this paper, we demonstrate the dynamic identification of the deformation of glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) in the state of vibration using an optical fiber distributed sensing system. We develop the optical fiber distributed sensing system which is capable of measuring the dynamic strain distribution based on OFDR. The OFDR system is made especially for high-speed measurements. We embed a fiber Bragg grating (FBG) with a continuous sensing range of 50 cm into glass fiber fabric and co-cure them with epoxy. The GFRP integrated with the FBG is cut into a beam. We apply vibrations of the resonant frequencies to the beam, and measure the strain distribution with a measurement rate of more than 800 sample per second. We calculate the deformation of the GFRP

beam based on the measured strain distribution. We compare the results with externally observed deformations by a high-speed camera and a laser displacement sensor. The applicability of the sensing system for the dynamic deformation monitoring of composites was investigated.

2 SENSING SYSTEM

We have developed a distributed sensing technique based on OFDR. The schematic of the OFDR system is shown in Fig. 1. The OFDR system consists of a laser source (GQ5510PLZ, Anritsu), a PC with A/D converter and two interferometers. The laser source can sweep the wavelength with the speed of 1.2 kHz. The sampling rate of the AD converter is 500 MHz. The system used in this study achieved the final measurement rate of more than 800S/s.

We use a long-length FBG with the length of 50 cm. This FBG has low reflectivity of a few per cent. In such a case, this expression is sufficient for the conceptual introduction of the OFDR [2]. Interferometer 2 as seen in Fig. 1 observes the interfered signal, D_2 , at detector D2 which is expressed as

$$D_2 = \sum_i R \cos(k2nL_i), \quad (1)$$

where R is the reflected spectrum of the i th section of the FBG, k is the wavenumber, n is the refractive index and L_i is the path difference between the reflector R3 and the i th section of the FBG. Equation 1 expresses that individual reflected spectra at arbitrary locations within the FBG has accompanying waves with individual frequencies which correspond to the reflection locations. This signal is sampled with a constant interval of the wavenumber which is triggered by the interferometer 1. In this paper the length of the ‘‘clock arm’’, L_R , is set as 2 m, which yields the sensing range of 1 m. By applying the short time Fourier transform (STFT) to D_2 , we can obtain spatial distributions of reflection spectra. In this paper, we adjusted signal processing parameters of STFT to achieve the spatial resolution of the distributed sensing as 0.6 mm.

Figure 1: Schematic of the OFDR system. D represents photo detector, C optical coupler and R reflector.

3 EXPERIMENT

We made a GFRP plate by hand-layup using four layers of bi-directional fabric and epoxy resin. The primary fibers are continuous orientated in 0/90 directions. We set the FBG with pre-tension at the surface of the laminated fabric and co-cured. The GFRP plate was cut into a beam. Figure 2 shows the manufactured GFRP beam. The optical fiber is totally embedded in the beam and the surface of the beam was smooth. The length, width and thickness of the beam were 470 mm, 20.6 mm and 3.09 mm, respectively.

Figure 3 shows the experimental setup. We clamped the beam so that 400 mm of the beam vibrated, and set the beam to a vibration exciter. For the reference of displacement measurements, we set a laser

displacement sensor and a high-speed camera. The laser displacement sensor was used for small displacement measurements, and the high-speed camera was used to measure displacements which were out of the sensing range of the laser displacement sensor. The measurement rate of the laser displacement sensor was 50 kHz. Both the laser displacement sensor and the high-speed camera measured displacements of the beam at four locations with 100 mm interval.

We applied vibrations of the resonant frequencies to the beam. The first and second resonant frequencies were 10.1 Hz and 62.8 Hz, respectively. We conducted strain distribution measurements by the OFDR system at each vibrating mode. The curvature of the beam, φ , was calculated as

$$\varphi = -\frac{\varepsilon}{y} = \frac{d^2u}{dx^2}, \quad (2)$$

where ε was measured strain, y is the distance from the neutral axis to the optical fiber core, x is the longitudinal distance from the clamped location and u is the deflection. The beam shape was determined by integrating the curvature.

Figure 2: Picture of the GFRP beam with the embedded FBG.

Figure 3: Picture of the experimental setup.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 4 shows time variations of measured strain distributions at first and second vibration modes. For both modes strains have peak values at the clamp location (position = 0 mm) and zero value at the beam edge (position = 400 mm). The strain distributions show one and two peaks in first and second modes, respectively, which correspond to the nodes of resonant vibration. It was demonstrated that the OFDR measurement system responded to the vibrating states of the beam.

We used the measured strain distributions to calculate the beam deflections. Figure 5 shows the time variations of estimated beam deflections at first and second vibration modes. It is seen that the deflection profiles of the resonant vibrations are clearly observed. Taking an example of the mode 2 vibration, Fig. 6 shows the time variation of the deflection at the beam edge (position = 400 mm) estimated by the OFDR system and observed by the laser displacement sensor. The estimation error distorted the waveform to some extent in the case of the OFDR, however, the amplitude and the frequency seemed to be agreed with the laser displacement sensor results. We applied Fourier transformation to calculate the frequency of the vibration. The calculated frequency was 62.9 Hz in the case of the OFDR and 62.6 Hz in the case of the laser displacement sensor. The consistent agreement was seen between the OFDR system, the laser displacement sensor and the vibration exciter, which demonstrated the applicability of the OFDR system to dynamic measurements.

We compared the estimated deflections with external observation results as seen in Fig. 7. Comparisons were shown at two phases of vibration where the beam edge was under maximum and minimum deflections. In the case of the first mode, measured deflections by the high-speed camera were plot with the OFDR results. In the case of the second mode, results of the laser displacement sensor were plot. The results of the OFDR and external observations agreed quantitatively in both cases of the first and second modes.

Figure 4: Time variation of strain distributions at individual vibration modes.

(a) First mode
(b) Second mode
Figure 5: Time variation of deflections at individual vibration modes.

(a) Estimated by the OFDR system

(b) Observed by the laser displacement sensor

Figure 6: Time variation of the deflections at the beam edge.

(a) First mode

(b) Second mode

Figure 7: Comparison of deflection estimated by the OFDR system (solid line) and by the external observation (circular plots) at individual vibration modes. The high-speed camera was used for the

external observation for the first mode, and the laser displacement sensor for the second mode.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We investigated the applicability of the dynamic deformation monitoring for the GFRP beam vibration using the OFDR systems. We embedded the FBG into the surface of the GFRP beam, and applied resonant vibrations to the beam. The OFDR system measured strain distributions with the sampling rate of more than 800S/s and the spatial resolution of 0.6 mm. Time variations of strain distributions were clearly observed for both cases of the first and second modes of vibrations. The beam deflections were estimated based on the measured strain distributions. With comparison of the external observation of deflections, it was demonstrated that the deflection profiles of the first and second vibration modes were accurately estimated.

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